

**Deliverable WP0.3 –
Sustainability document
OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP5**

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34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA,
45-RUOKA, UCPH

Former partners: 12-DTU, 17-UCM

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-WP0.3 – Sustainability document		
WP and task	WP0-T4 – Sustainability		
Leader	13-SSI		
Other contributors	1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WbvR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA, 45-RUOKA, UCPH		
Due month of the deliverable	M58		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R: report Save date: 7-Dec-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHJEP dissemination plans Social Media: n.a. Other recipient(s): n.a.		

JIP MATRIX SUSTAINABILITY DOCUMENT

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Definitions

The MATRIX project utilized the following definitions from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)'s¹ evaluation criteria:

- Impact – The extent to which the intervention has generated or is expected to generate significant positive or negative, intended or unintended, higher-level effects
- Sustainability – The extent to which the net benefits of the intervention continue, or are likely to continue

¹ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; Home; Development; Co-operation Directorate; Evaluation of development programmes; Evaluation Criteria [Online]. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/dac/evaluation/daccriteriaforevaluatingdevelopmentassistance.htm#relevance-block>

The MATRIX project of the One Health EJP

MATRIX is a project of the [One Health European Joint Programme \(OHEJP\)](#), a partnership of 44 food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the [Med-Vet-Net Association](#).

The project started in January 2020 and per December 2022 (date of end of the project), the MATRIX Consortium was made of 19 partner institutes representing the animal health, public health and food safety sectors from 12 European countries. More information about the project can be found [here](#).

The objective of MATRIX is to create practical solutions for European countries to help support and advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance. These solutions are known as the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**. Annex 1 of this document provides an overview of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**.

MATRIX invites European institutes working in the animal health, public health and food safety sectors to adopt these solutions and further build upon them.

MATRIX ensures that the developed solutions are relevant to the surveillance of specific hazards. The hazards of interest, hereafter referred to as Hazard Tracks (HT), were chosen based on the operational priorities of MATRIX partner institutes as well as their One Health relevance. They are *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance.

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – background

The original MATRIX project proposal and work plan state:

- “Sustainability refers specifically to the maintenance of project outputs after its conclusion”
- “The main contributor to sustainability is MATRIX’s focus on ‘adoption in practice’ in individual countries”
- “The sustainability of the outputs from MATRIX lies primarily with each country that chooses to adopt the proposed frameworks”
- “The expected gains in surveillance quality and/or efficiency will be the main driver for countries to keep their adoption”
- “Maintaining sustainability and extending the MATRIX approach is up to the individual countries, but the frameworks will be kept publicly available”
- “MATRIX is sustainable as almost all outputs will be made freely available to stakeholders

after the project has ended”

- The project operates to the “continuous identification and documentation of sustainability challenges and opportunities to address them”

MATRIX is designed in a way that most of its impact, which primarily depends on the use that others will make of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**, is expected after the project ends. Logically, this pushes the sustainability of the change operated by the project after the project's completion, making it beyond the control of the project itself.

Therefore, MATRIX had always a primary interest in spreading the knowledge of its work and promoting the solutions that it develops.

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – the MATRIX Consortium meeting in November 2021

In November 2021, the 19 partners comprising the MATRIX Consortium agreed to maintain a continuous focus on the project's sustainability during 2022 and until its end. This made the project's sustainability strategy a shared commitment and responsibility of all partners.

The MATRIX Consortium worked and agreed on a sustainability strategy to be applied in 2022, when the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** were finalized.

The project's sustainability strategy is built around the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** and it includes 5 action points:

1. To support MATRIX partners in making use of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**. This point focuses on actors that are internal to the MATRIX Consortium
2. To disseminate and pilot the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** among non-partners. This point focuses on actors that are external to the MATRIX Consortium
3. To support the production of original peer-reviewed publications
4. To continue and whenever possible enhance training/dissemination activities aiming to reach out for the broadest audience
5. To continue the advancement and use of the OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform ([here](#))

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – 5 actions

To support MATRIX partners in making use of the MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance

The MATRIX Consortium developed a self-assessment tool to support MATRIX partners defining how they are using, plan to use or could use the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** in their respective countries. This process started from the following questions:

- What MATRIX can do for my country?
- What can I (as a partner institute) do to facilitate this process?

MATRIX partners utilized the self-assessment tool throughout 2022 until the end of the project. The project partners were continuously invited to update their own assessment and share it with other partners (e.g. during operational and Consortium meetings) to inspire each other.

The self-assessment tool comprises of the following topics:

What MATRIX output is/could be relevant to your institute and/or country?	
Is the output already in use at you institute/in your country? Could it be used? Is there any plan to use it (before/after the end of MATRIX)?	
What is the problem/situation that this MATRIX output can/could help to solve? What is missing today that this MATRIX output can provide?	
What is the context of use for this MATRIX output, including sector(s) and/or hazard of relevance?	
What is your desired outcome/situation by using this MATRIX output?	
If the considered MATRIX output is currently not finalized, what do you expect from the output?	
What is a possible way forward/action plan for you to use this MATRIX output (with/without a timeline)?	

This exercise was deemed necessary in view of:

- The mutated global scenario since the project was first conceived, mainly due to the Covid-19 pandemic

- The high turnover of the project's partners and members to ensure a continuous sense of ownership towards the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**

It was clarified that none of the conclusions of the self-assessment could ever be considered an official commitment to the actual application of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** by the partner institutes after the end of the project.

To disseminate and pilot the MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance among non-partners

This action addressed the original intent of the project to reach out to so-called “non-partners”². Despite not actually being described as an action in the Annual Work Plans (AWP) for Year 3 (2020), Year 4 (2021) and Year 5 (2022), reaching out to “non-partners” was a relevant opportunity to reinforce the project sustainability. It is worth highlighting that some MATRIX Work Packages had already reached out to “non-partners” for the specific objectives of their work before this action of the MATRIX sustainability strategy was put in place.

This action took place in Year 5 (2022), when most of the project's outputs eventually became available for dissemination and piloting. Thanks to a close collaboration with the OHEJP Communication Team, a series of seven webinars was organized in 2022 for the purpose of this action.

The **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars** presented the solutions developed by MATRIX. During the webinars, participants learned about the solutions, their intended use and ongoing status of implementation. Participants also had the opportunity to directly influence the ongoing refinement of the solutions by sharing their own experiences and needs associated with One Health Surveillance. Surveillance officers, researchers and managers from institutes in Europe who work on One Health Surveillance in the animal health, human health, food safety, environmental and other relevant sectors were invited (free of charge) to participate in the **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars**. The latest update of the dissemination flyer is available [here](#).

The last webinar in the series was organized with the objective to summarize the lessons learned throughout the MATRIX project through the lens of its Hazard Tracks. The webinar was organized to

² “Non-partners” here means food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and beyond that are not members of the MATRIX Consortium. See the original MATRIX project proposal at pages 10, 17 and 18.

point out what makes *Listeria*, *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* different in a One Health Surveillance context, as well as how these and other foodborne hazards can be tackled using the same set of tools.

To support the production of original peer-reviewed publications

Peer-reviewed publications are key to ensure the sustainability of MATRIX and similar integrative projects. Together with OHEJP Joint Integrative Projects (JIP) CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP, we prepared a thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health Surveillance.

This call was launched in the Journal *Frontiers in Public Health* to offer an additional opportunity of visibility and dissemination to the work of our projects and to collect some of the achievements of the JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies. The call is available [here](#).

To continue and whenever possible enhance training/dissemination activities aiming to reach out for the broadest audience

This action is rooted in the original project proposal and work plan, under the *MATRIX Work Package 5, Task 4 – Training and Dissemination*, and it naturally is a substantial part of the MATRIX sustainability strategy.

To continue the advancement and use of the OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform

This action is rooted in the original project proposal and work plan, under the *MATRIX Work Package 5, Task 3 – Knowledge-Integration Platform*, and it naturally is a substantial part of the MATRIX sustainability strategy.

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – the MATRIX Consortium meeting in March 2022

In March 2022, the 19 partners comprising the MATRIX Consortium gathered for a hybrid meeting (in-person and online) in Berlin, Germany. The meeting had a dedicated session in the afternoon of March 17th to discuss the legacy of the OHEJP JIPs, as a prerequisite to frame the sustainability of our work. In addition to the full MATRIX Consortium, participants included representatives from the

OHEJP Project Management Team and Work Packages, OHEJP Stakeholders, other OHEJP Projects and other One Health Initiatives and Projects. The programme of this session is reported here:

March 17th – Thursday

13.00-13.15	The legacy of OHEJP projects This session brought together different experiences to reflect about the legacy of OHEJP JIP. The session took place as a series of presentations and discussions.
13.15-13.45	From the first to the second call of JIPs – ORION & MATRIX
13.45-14.15	From the first to the second call of JIPs – COHESIVE & MATRIX
14.15-14.30	Break
14.30-15.15	The second call of JIPs – CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP & MATRIX
15.15-15.45	Beyond OHEJP – updates from the RAKIP initiative. More information here
15.45-16.00	Break
16.00-16.30	Beyond OHEJP – updates from the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SIS OT), an operational tool of the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide by WHO/FAO/OIE. More information here
16.30-17.00	Beyond OHEJP – Food Safety and the Consumers' Perspective: our ultimate Goal. The SafeConsumE experience. More information here

The following image summarises the relevant discussion regarding the legacy of the OHEJP JIPs_

The following topics were discussed at the OHEJP MATRIX Consortium meeting on March 17th, 2022 during a session with representatives from JIPs ORION, COHESIVE, CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP and MATRIX

- Some initiatives from JIPs of the first call are now continuing into JIPs of the second call**
e.g. the work of JIP ORION about the OHS CODEX: Knowledge Integration Platform is now continuing in JIP MATRIX; the work of JIP COHESIVE about guidelines to support countries to strengthen One Health collaborations is now continuing in JIP MATRIX.
- Where will the initiatives of JIPs of the second call continue?**
- JIPs have been and are exploring opportunities outside of OHEJP to advance their achievements after 2022**
- MATRIX aims to develop Solutions for OHS. However, their use depends on countries that choose to adopt them or not**
- There is a need to move forward, from the dissemination of JIPs' outputs towards the sustainability of the change operated by JIPs**
- What is the expected change of JIPs?**
e.g. for MATRIX, change is expected in the actual creation of the Solutions for OHS (the objective of the project), not in their use

Key Themes:

- Role of OHEJP partner institutes and countries
- JIPs' sense of ownership and co-financing
- Turnover of HR
- Permanence of partner institutes

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – the MATRIX Final meeting in September 2022

In September 2022, the 19 partners of the MATRIX Consortium gathered for a meeting (in-person only) in Copenhagen, Denmark. The meeting opened on September 20th together with the OHEJP JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP as well as a few selected representatives of the OHEJP Project Management Team and OHEJP Stakeholders. This was another valuable opportunity to discuss about the legacy of OHEJP JIPs. The programme of the session is reported here:

Agenda September 20, 2022

09.00-09.20	Arrival and welcome
09.20-09.30	Introduction to the meeting
09.30-09.50	Keynote: The relevance of OHEJP JIP from a Danish perspective
09.50-10.10	Keynote: The relevance of OHEJP JIP from an international perspective
10.10-10.30	Keynote: The future of the One Health European Joint Programme and opportunities for countries
10.30-11.00	<i>Break</i>
11.00-11.20	Keynote: One Health in Europe: what do we need from a food safety perspective
11.20-12.20	JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP
12.20-13.30	<i>Lunch</i>
13.30-14.30	JIP CARE
14.30-15.30	JIP MATRIX
15.30-16.00	<i>Break</i>
16.00-16.45	Round table – The legacy of JIP
16.45-17.00	<i>Closure</i>
18.00-21.00	<i>Social dinner</i>

Representatives of JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX, and of the OHEJP Project Management Team and of OHEJP Stakeholders participated in the final round table. The following were the highlights of the discussion:

- Now that the JIPs have delivered what was promised, it is time to return to the stakeholders of the programme, those who envisaged it. The legacy of JIPs lies in the needs of those who can utilize and advance the knowledge generated by the projects
- Countries and partner institutes have the opportunity to utilize and advance the knowledge generated by the projects, also in consideration of the large investments they made into OHEJP

- Social sciences are key to ensure a change in the knowledge, attitudes and practices of many individuals across different sectors and at different levels of the decision-making process in the direction of One Health
- Studying the cost-effectiveness of One Health is another opportunity to secure the necessary attention that the approach requires

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – results

To support MATRIX partners in making use of the MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance

The self-assessment tool developed to support the MATRIX partners defining how they are using, plan to use or could use the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** in their respective countries was applied by several partners throughout 2022. Results were shared by partners during routine operational and Consortium meetings. Specifically, a session was organized during the final day of the MATRIX Consortium meeting in March 2022 in Berlin, Germany. There, a few partners presented their initiatives and ideas to the project Consortium and the invited representatives from the OHEJP Project Management Team and Work Packages, OHEJP stakeholders, other OHEJP projects and other One Health initiatives and projects.

Partners showed how they applied different strategies to cascade the utilization of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** within their countries. For example:

- The implementation of one solution can open the door to promote the others at country level
- Different institutes from the same country (e.g. representing the human and animal sectors) decided to use the self-assessment tool together
- Partners showed interest in the use of each other's solutions, whether they participated in their development or not. This was highlighted as a success in terms of project ownership.

Partners also reported that it is key to maintain a focus on the operational problems that the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** can help solving at country level.

The results of this continuous self-assessment are in the hands of the MATRIX partners and it is up to them to take initiative and build upon the identified interests and opportunities after the end of the project. This is in line with the project's original strategy: "The sustainability of the outputs from MATRIX lies primarily with each country that chooses to adopt the proposed frameworks".

Here below are a few examples of the input given by MATRIX partners while conducting this self-assessment:

<i>Questions</i>	<i>Examples *</i>
Is there any plan to use it (before/after the end of MATRIX)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some partners explored the opportunity to pilot and utilize the MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance e.g. at the local level in their respective country
What is the problem/situation that this MATRIX output can/could help to solve?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gaps in cross-sectoral and sector-specific surveillance capacities Difficulties locating resources and experiences to achieve sectorial collaborations Need to apply a One Health approach to Whole-genome Sequencing-based surveillance
What is missing today that this MATRIX output can provide?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better preparedness and surveillance of infectious diseases including zoonoses
What is the context of use for this MATRIX output, including sector(s) and/or hazard of relevance?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internally and externally at the specific institute level between institutions within the same sector and between sectors at the local/national level
What is your desired outcome/situation by using this MATRIX output?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved multi-sectoral collaborations Establishment of a One Health, hazard-specific, context-specific surveillance system
What is a possible way forward/action plan for you to use this MATRIX output (with/without a timeline)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep active the developed networks/collaborations and exchange of best practices across countries and sectors Identification of national contact points

* These examples are from various partners and do not refer to any specific country, hazard or **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** in particular.

To disseminate and pilot the MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance among non-partners

The **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars** presented the solutions developed by MATRIX to support and advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance in European countries. Below is a calendar and reach of the specific webinars.

Date and number of participants who registered and attended the **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars** (update 30-11-2022):

<i>Webinar</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>attended</i>	<i>registered</i>
OH-EPICAP TOOL	19-05-2022	30	56
FOOD SAFETY KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE (FSKX) FORMAT	08-06-2022	17	35
MANUAL FOR ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE DASHBOARDS	15-09-2022	34	64
ROADMAP TO DEVELOP NATIONAL ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE	06-10-2022	24	52
ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE CODEX: KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION PLATFORM	10-11-2022	21	53
INTERACTIVE GUIDE TO DEVELOPING MULTI-SECTORAL SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS	24-11-2022	31	68
WHAT IS SPECIAL AND COMMON FOR FOODBORNE HAZARDS IN ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE?	15-12-2022		
	Total	157	351

Country representation and number of registered participants in the **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars** (update 30-11-2022):

Country representation and number of attending participants in the **Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe webinars** (update 30-11-2022)

To support the production of original peer-reviewed publications.

JIPs MATRIX, CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP jointly launched the thematic call titled “One Health Surveillance in Practice: Experiences of Integration among Human Health, Animal Health, Environmental Health, and Food Safety Sectors” in the peer-reviewed journal *Frontiers in Public Health* ([here](#)). The call had the following topic:

Recognizing that human and animal health are interconnected brings along the challenge of integrating their respective health systems, including routine disease surveillance activities, outbreak management, and emergency preparedness. However, approaches in these different sectors are still unaligned in many ways, including their respective agendas, both at the country and the supranational levels. Several initiatives have been launched to study and tackle this problem. Since the early 2000s, the World Health Organization (WHO), the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO), and the World Organization of Animal Health (OIE) paved the road of multi-sectorial One Health approaches and collaborations, leading to the recent publication of the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide. In Europe, the “One Health European Joint Programme” aims at fostering the transdisciplinary cooperation of activities that are relevant to One Health within and across European countries. Furthermore, various scientific networks and consortia have been set up to bring together professionals and experiences from different sectors.

Integration is key to the One Health agenda, and to the challenge of future preparedness and response to foodborne pathogens and other emerging threats, both from an epidemiological and microbiological perspective. This Research Topic aims at describing first-hand, successful, inspirational (and possibly visionary), experiences about the integration of approaches, procedures and methodologies for One Health surveillance across the human health, animal health, environmental health, and food safety sectors, at the local, national, or supranational levels.

Within the overarching domain of One Health surveillance, this Research Topic welcomes experiences of integration in the domains of routine surveillance, outbreak management and preparedness, especially those based on active inter-sectorial collaborations, with the broadest range of stakeholders, both public and private. This Research Topic has a focus on – but is not limited to:

- The design, implementation and evaluation of integrated surveillance programs;
- Laboratory methods, reference materials and data;
- Data and specimen sharing;
- Interpretation of surveillance data, communication, and response, within and across sectors;
- Integrative experiences from the prevention and control of hazards of cross-sectorial relevance (including *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, *Listeria*, pathogenic *E. coli* and cross-pathotypes in *E. coli*, among others) and emerging threats (including the challenge of antimicrobial resistance).

Furthermore, research assessing One Health capacities and capabilities, designing integrated surveillance systems and their evaluation, fits the scope of this Research Topic, including the introduction of innovative tools.

The primary geographic focus is on the European context, from the regional, national and peripheral levels, encouraging cross-country and cross-sector collaborations both from quantitative and qualitative sciences.

Given the deadline on 31-12-2022, the call yielded the following results (as per 31-10-2022).

Manuscript published	2
Authors	14
Call total views (over 5 continents)	2157
Article views	677
Article downloads	133
Topic views	1347

To continue and whenever possible enhance training/dissemination activities aiming to reach out for the broadest audience

All training and dissemination activities conducted by the MATRIX Consortium under the umbrella of the MATRIX *Work Package 5, Task 4 – Training and Dissemination* are relevant achievements in line with this action. All MATRIX partners contributed to the training and dissemination of the knowledge generated by the project.

The One Health Surveillance Briefings (e.g. webinars or meetings; see the MATRIX Final Report) informed partners, representatives from other OHEJP projects and beyond, and stakeholders such as the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) about the project advancements and results. By the end of October 2022, more than 50 events were conducted. The final project report will fully document these activities.

To continue the advancement and use of the OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform

The development of the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* progressed from 2020 to 2022 in frequent task-specific meetings under the leadership of the MATRIX partner 9-BfR – the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung – [here](#)).

The OHS Codex, which was developed in the JIP ORION, was extended to serve as a Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) for MATRIX as well. This was done by adding a new principle that focuses on surveillance planning and management, updating the existing principles and including new methods, training materials and examples of One Health Surveillance reports.

The *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform* is included in the toolbox of the Surveillance and information sharing operational tool (SIS OT): an operational tool of the tripartite zoonoses guide, by World Health Organization (WHO), Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH, former OIE) – [here](#).

Additionally, during the MATRIX operational meeting held on May 18th 2022, the leaders of the MATRIX Work Packages, Tasks and Hazard Tracks discussed the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** in view of the updated principles of the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform*. They agreed on where each of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** fits into the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform*. This was relevant to define how the stand-alone solutions are related and interconnected (see below):

<i>OHS Codex/KIP Principles</i>	<i>MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance</i>
1. The Planning and Management principle: Supporting the whole OHS process	→ OH-EpiCap tool (WP4) – Rodmap (WP5) – Best practices (WP2) – Guideline for official controls in FS (WP3)
2. The Collaboration principle: Supporting OHS collaboration & cross-sectorial communication	→ Guide to develop multi-sectoral surveillance systems (WP1)
3. The Knowledge principle: Improving the OHS knowledge base	→ FSKX – Dashboard repository and manual (WP6)
4. The Data principle: Supporting OHS Data interoperability, integration & interpretation	
5. The Dissemination principle: Supporting external communication of OHS outcomes	

The MATRIX Sustainability Strategy – challenges

Sustainability challenges and opportunities to address them were continuously assessed and identified during the life of the project.

In January 2021, the National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU Food) left the MATRIX Consortium. Despite the scientific loss related to the specific DTU Food expertise in food safety, the Consortium managed to take over the related activities. The remaining MATRIX partners efficiently redistributed the related activities and resources accordingly. From the MATRIX Year 4 (2021) Annual Report:

About the redistribution of the 12-DTU Food activities, this included: i) expanding the evaluation of the EU-Epi-Cap [now renamed OH-EpiCap] tool by 1-ANSES, 23-UoS and 13-SSI; ii) strengthening the involvement of 33-NVI in WP2-T3, WP5-T1 and WP 6; iii) expanding the work of WP3 including output-based surveillance of *Echinococcus M.* by 34-PIWET; iv) including a concept called "Forum for preparedness epidemiology" in the work of WP5 by 41-SVA; v) extending the work at 13-SSI in WP5-T2. The remaining budget was temporarily placed to 13-SSI for later allocation to the project consortium e.g. to support more participants to the final project meeting.

Before that, partner VISAVET-University Complutense, Madrid (17-UCM) left the project Consortium in 2020. Additionally, the originally intended collaboration with the Ross University School of Veterinary Medicine on the Caribbean island of St. Kitts never started due to the loss of key personnel. The original project members of several partners were replaced by new colleagues. This not only affected the operational aspects of the project, but also the overall sense of ownership of the project. The project sustainability strategy, especially with action 1, aimed to reinforce the sense of ownership among the project's partners.

In autumn 2021, the original project proposal was reviewed and compared to the AWP's Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5. Discrepancies were found among the different documents. Particularly, discrepancies were found about the Work Plan as described on pages 11-14 of the original project proposal document. Considering this, it is important to highlight that the only documents guiding the activities of the different MATRIX WPs were the AWP's Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5, in line with the related yearly budgets. From the MATRIX Year 4 (2021) Annual Report:

The original project proposal (page 21) describes integrative missions around the MATRIX HTs but these are not mentioned in the AWP's Year 3, Year 4 and Year 5 and their related budgets. However, in consideration of the impact that HTs can have beyond the project, HTs and WP0 initiated an exchange about the possibility to summarise the lessons learnt during the work of specific HTs into one or more webinars and/or peer-reviewed publications in view of the end of the project.

[...]

The original project proposal describes the project's outputs several times using different words i.e. under "objectives description" at page 7, "primary impacts" at page 9, "progresses beyond state-of-the-art" at page 10, "project aims" at page 10, "objectives" under Annex 7 of the original project proposal at page 24.

Finally, it is worth highlighting another challenge to the sustainability of MATRIX, and possibly of many other OHEJP projects. MATRIX developed the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** thanks to the partner-specific project resources. In line with the original project proposal, MATRIX partners made the solutions available to the public audience either on the specific-partner institute websites, on GitHub or Zenodo. Currently, the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** are hosted in different spaces.

The dispersal of the work of MATRIX (and in general of other OHEJP projects) over time is a challenge to their sustainability. Ideally, OHEJP can now ensure the sustainable hosting of the projects' outputs in a common platform.

The legacy of MATRIX – One Health impact

The MATRIX Sustainability strategy was in line with the *OHEJP priority (sustainable) activities – The 7 Wonders of OHEJP* as was presented during the OHEJP ASM 2022 in Orvieto (Terni), Italy (see the image below):

- Point 3 -integrating & exchanging knowledge;
- Point 4 - implementing, strengthening and assessing One Health surveillance;
- Point 6 -, fostering (inter)national collaborations.

MATRIX created practical solutions for European countries to support and advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance i.e. the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** (Annex 1). The impact and sustainability of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** now

depends on their adoption in practice by individual institutes and countries e.g. to evaluate current surveillance systems, to utilize Systems Thinking along the roadmap towards integrated One Health Surveillance, and to develop One Health Surveillance dashboards. International stakeholders can also utilize, disseminate and build upon the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** e.g. by facilitating evaluation activities across countries and/or hazards with the OH-EpiCap tool or by promoting the *OHS Codex: The Knowledge Information Platform*.

MATRIX ensured that the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance** are relevant to different countries, which are at different stages of their One Health Surveillance development. For example:

- The OH-EpiCap tool specifically addresses the context-specific capacities and capabilities of any country or region by supporting the identification of areas in the studied surveillance system that could lead to improvements in the organization of collaborations across sectors, the extent of collaborations in operational activities, the impact of multi-sectoral collaborations on surveillance.
- The roadmap to develop national One Health Surveillance can be used by countries to develop One Health Surveillance according to their needs and resources. Countries can use it either to build a new One Health Surveillance system or to advance an existing one.
- The manual for One Health Surveillance dashboards is a toolbox and a companion for developers, future, and current implementers of One Health Surveillance dashboards, which make use of open-source tools.
- The interactive guide to developing multi-sectoral surveillance systems specifically starts from existing animal health, public health and food safety surveillance systems at country level, providing seven generic steps towards integrating sectoral surveillance systems.
- Best practices operationalize cross-sectorial collaborations, which are rooted in a collection of maps of surveillance chains and cross-sectorial linkages for different hazards and from different countries. This ensures that the best practices can be operationalized to answer various objectives.
- The guideline to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the food sector using output-based standards is written both for those who already implement surveillance with output-based standards and those who do not, yet.

Beyond MATRIX, ownership is now key to ensure the use of the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**.

Contacts

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ANNEX 1 – The outputs of MATRIX: Solutions for One Health Surveillance

Annex 1 of this document provides an overview of the outputs of MATRIX, the **MATRIX Solutions for One Health Surveillance**.

OH-EpiCap Tool

OH-EpiCap Tool – an interactive tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS of a hazard of choice, identifying strengths and places for improvement. Additionally, the tool allows the benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities for comparison. More information is available here: [OH-EpiCap tool flyer](#) and [OH-EpiCap tool user guide](#).

Leading partners: Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, France (ANSES) and University of Surrey, United Kingdom (UoS). Contact: Viviane Henaux (Viviane.HENAUX@anses.fr) and Joaquin Prada (j.prada@surrey.ac.uk)

Roadmap to develop national One Health Surveillance

Roadmap to develop national OHS – a guideline that countries can use to develop OHS according to their needs and resources. The roadmap expanded the work of the OHEJP COHESIVE project and is available at <https://www.ohras.eu/page/home> – copy-paste this link in your browser)

Leading partner: National Veterinary Institute, Sweden (SVA). Contact: Mia Holmberg (mia.holmberg@sva.se) and Estelle Ågren (estelle.agren@sva.se)

Manual for One Health Surveillance Dashboards

Manual for OHS Dashboards – This is an online dashboard inventory and practical manual to facilitate the design and implementation of OHS dashboards using open-source tools. More information is available here: [Dashboard Information Centre](#).

Leading partners: National Veterinary Institute, Sweden (SVA) & Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Norway (NIPH). Contact: Wiktor Gustafsson (wiktor.gustafsson@sva.se) and Gry Marysol Groneng (GryMarysol.Groneng@fhi.no)

Interactive guide to developing multi-sectoral surveillance systems

An interactive guide to facilitate the development of multi-sectoral OHS frameworks from existing animal health, public health and food safety surveillance systems. A beta version available [here](#).

Leading partner: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Germany (FLI). Contact: Johanna Dups-bergmann (Johanna.Dups-Bergmann@fli.de) and Carola Sauter-Louis (Carola.Sauter-Louis@fli.de)

Best practices to operationalize cross-sectorial collaborations

Best-practices to operationalize cross-sectorial collaborations with a focus on data collection, data sharing, data analysis, and the dissemination of surveillance results ([here](#)). This work builds upon a report about the mapping of surveillance chains and cross-sectorial linkages for different hazards, which is available [here](#).

Leading partner: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise, Italy (IZSAM). Contact: Francesca Cito (f.cito@izs.it) and Laura Amato (l.amato@izs.it)

A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the food sector using output-based standards

A guide to design, implement, and evaluate official controls within the FS using output-based standards ([here](#)).

Leading partners: Animal and Plant Health Agency, United Kingdom (APHA) & National Veterinary Research Institute, Poland (PIWET). Contact: Verity Horigan (verity.horigan@apha.gov.uk) and Maciej.Kochanowski (maciej.kochanowski@piwet.pulawy.pl)

MATRIX also promotes and expands the following initiative:

The One Health Surveillance CODEX: The Knowledge Integration Platform – this is a framework to integrate various resources that help to implement OHS in all sectors ([here](#)).

Leading partner: German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR). Contact: Matthias Filter (Matthias.Filter@bfr.bund.de)

Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format – this is a format that supports the One Health community in sharing and re-using mathematical models as well as data analysis procedures ([here](#)).

Leading partner: German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR). Contact: Matthias Filter (Matthias.Filter@bfr.bund.de)